

MSc Chemistry

Analytical track

Master Thesis

Chemical fingerprinting of firework clay plaques, by XRF and indirect UV detection CE.

**An effort to aid police and forensic institutions in the
prevention and investigation of crimes using pyrotechnics.**

by

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Abstract

Fireworks are popular means of celebration all over the world, but they also cause a lot of damages when used illegally. In an effort to reduce the production and distribution of illegal fireworks and to link fireworks that are used in criminal acts, our group set out on finding chemical markers that can separate or connect firework evidence. This work is focused on clay plaques used in fireworks as stoppers, which confine the gas released by ignition and force the gas to escape in the desired direction. These plaques were cut from post blast fireworks and analyzed by X-ray fluorescence (XRF) and capillary zone electrophoresis (CE). Quantitative elemental data obtained from XRF was treated by principal component analysis (PCA) and partial least square regression discriminant analysis (PLS-DA). These statistical results can group the studied samples by province, city and even by factory. To increase the amount of information on the clay, the clay plaques were also analyzed by CE with indirect UV detection, using a method proposed by Soga and Ross (1999) for the analysis of small anions, carbohydrates and amino acids. Alanine and serine are the only two amino acids which were possibly in our clay samples. This CE method was also used for nonspecific sample discrimination with an optimized sample extraction. Inter-sample differences were found with this method, but no conclusive sample grouping could be achieved on the bases of the CE results. Overall, when combined, the tools set up in this work look promising for creating a chemical fingerprint which can individualize fireworks and distinguish their origin.

1. Introduction

Illegal fireworks can cause a lot of harm upon people. Aside from its economic pushback of a part of industry which provides jobs to almost a million people in china alone; illegal productions are often dangerous workplaces. Between 2015 and 2017 illegal factories in China accounted for 53.3% of fatal workplace accidents in firework production¹. In addition, illegal fireworks often lack the safety features which regulated fireworks adhere to, meaning consumers are also at greater risk of accidents, causing minor or sometimes even fatal injuries². While these are mostly accidental misuses of explosives there is a whole other side, criminal use. In the Netherlands around New Year's Eve 2016/2017, there was approximately €14 million in damages to private property, even more to government property³. These damages, along with the damages and loot from ATM robberies where fireworks are used, are costing our societies a concerning amount.

In an effort to reduce the production and distribution of illegal fireworks and to link fireworks that are used in criminal acts, our group set out on finding chemical markers that can separate or connect firework evidence. In doing so there are several parts of a firework to consider, figure 1A. The black/flash powder for instance, both before and after the article has been set off, which are usually analyzed for small ions, using techniques such as capillary electrophoresis with contactless conductivity detection⁴, gas chromatography mass spectrometry⁵, microfluidics⁶ and many more. This ion composition can be useful for identifying the type of explosive used, but the sample collection method is prone to contaminations and can be limited by the number of different ions it can measure for identification. A novel more effective technique for this analysis using IC-MS is being worked on and validated currently at Netherlands forensic institute (NFI), who are also investigating the fuses used to light the firework. The ink used in the packaging could also inform on the authenticity of the firework. Techniques for such work are available; looking at oils, dyes and small ions^{7,8}, most from the field of fraud and cultural heritage. However, no ink analysis study other than simple visual inspection⁹ has been performed on fireworks specifically as of writing this paper. This could involve additional challenges because it is printed, not written and it can contain contaminating ions from the explosion or from lying on the ground at a crime scene. The plastic caps at the bottom of fireworks, figure 1A, have been studied extensively in previous work at the NFI from Bezemer et al¹⁰. However, not all fireworks contain these plastic caps, more options should be considered. The final subject of investigation is the clay plaques. Clay is used in fireworks to confine the gas released by ignition and to force the gas to escape in the desired direction. In a firecracker for example the clay is used at both the top and the bottom, figure 1A, this to build up pressure which will burst the cardboard at the sides and cause a bang. Little work is focused on the chemical composition of clay specifically, most geochemical research is focused on soil in general, but rarely on clay alone^{11,12,13}. The few papers that do focus on the chemical composition of clays are usually in the field of archeology¹⁴ not forensics.

In this paper, analysis is focused on clay. Clay was chosen as a subject of interest because it stays mostly, if not partially, physically intact after an explosion, allowing samples to be taken from the core of the clay plaque decreasing the amount of cross contamination. It was also chosen because it is chemically diverse in nature; All clays consist of alternating sheets of tetrahedral SiO₂ and octahedral metal oxide often Al₂O₃ (sometimes Mg or Fe). The nature in which these sheets interconnect, shown schematically in figure 1B, causes the outside layers to form hydroxide groups, creating a polar habitat in which water, cations¹⁵ and polar organic compounds^{16,17}, like amino acids^{16,17} lignins^{16,17} or sugars^{16,17,18} can be contained, hence the chemical diversity. Some clays have two sheets, some have

three, kaolinite and montmorillonite are respective examples. The type of clay can be identified by the sheet composition as well as the dominant exchangeable cations such as Fe, Mg, K and other alkali metals^{15,19}. However, for our research purposes the type of clay is unlikely to be sufficient information for discriminating between fireworks, this because a lot of firework productions as well as their illegal counterparts are based in similar geographical locations. This will be further explained in the sample information section. Our hypothesis is that firework factories will get the clay from the nearest provider to save cost, thus little variation in the type of clay is to be expected. This means simple analyses, for instance X-ray diffraction^{20,21,22} or cation exchange capacity^{23,24}, are unlikely to provide sufficient information to conclude in which factory or city the clay was processed. A more specific marker is needed to individualize the articles, for instance: what specific quarry did it come from? What binder was used? Do the manufacturers add anything?

To find such markers, we analyzed the clay using X-ray fluorescence (XRF) and capillary electrophoresis (CE). XRF utilizes x-rays to energize electrons in order to knock them out of an atom's electron shell. Electrons from other shells fall into the now unoccupied ground state position. During this process a photon is emitted, where the energy of this photon is depended on the difference in shell electron energies, which in turn is dependent on the element from which it came. The XRF measures the energy of the photon and how many of this type of photon are emitted. Based on these two factors, it provides information on which elements are in your sample and their abundance. This information was collected and treated with chemometrics. Quantitative elemental data

Figure 1: A: a schematic cross section of a cobra 6 firework. Figure obtained from K. Bezemer et al. 2019 *Forensic Chemistry* (under review, submitted 30th of April 2019). B: a schematic representation of the sheet composition and interlinking in kaolin clay. Obtained with from *Fundamentals of environmental chemistry*, Manahan 1993³³.

from the XRF was analyzed by principal component analysis (PCA) and partial least square regression discriminant analysis (PLS-DA). These statistical tools provide distinction between clay samples by calculating the level of inter sample element composition differences. Because the XRF bases its quantification on a standard the method is classified as semi-quantitative. As it would be useful to test firework evidence in the field, at a customs office or a mobile forensics lab for instance, this work utilized a portable XRF machine. These analyzers are fast and easy to operate, making them ideal for fieldwork. The downsides to portable XRF are its large margin of error for quantification compared to its static counterpart and its lack of molecular structural information. However, the error is acceptable for our uses and the lack of structural information is addressed by comparison of elemental compositions regardless of structure, along with the use of complimentary techniques.

One of these complimentary techniques is CE. To gain information alongside the XRF data, the clays were analyzed by CE. This technique was used in an attempt to gain knowledge on the types of compounds adsorbed to the clay. CE uses the power of electrical current to migrate ions and separates them based on their mass to charge ratio (m/z). For this research a CE method using indirect UV detection proposed by Soga and Ross (1999)²⁵ was adapted and used to test the abundance of possible clay adhered carbohydrates, small ions and amino acids. This same technique was also used as a proof of concept for nonspecific sample discrimination. Nonspecific because the peaks used to find differences in samples are of unknown origin. To find as many data points as possible for the nonspecific discrimination, the effectiveness of several protocols for the extraction of compounds from clay were investigated.

The ultimate aim of this project is to use the information obtained from the analysis of clay plaques to create a chemical fingerprint which can individualize fireworks and distinguish their origin. In order to attain this goal, clay plaques will be analyzed using first a non-destructive portable XRF where data will be interpreted using chemometric tools. Followed by an optimized sample extraction, leading to analysis by CE.

2. Materials and method

2.1 Reagents

Hydrochloric acid (HCl), sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄) and sodium hydroxide (NaOH) were used for clay extractions. The CE background electrolyte (BGE) consisted of 20mM 2,6-pyridinedicarboxylic acid (PDC), 0.5 mM Hexadecyltrimethylammonium hydroxide (CTAH,

25% in methanol) in deionized water, adjusted to pH=12.1 with NaOH. Bioreagent grade mineral oil was used for the oil overlays. All were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Zwijndrecht, Netherlands). Deionized water from a Merck reference MilliQ dispenser. A stock solution of amino acids was made at a concentration of 10 g/L in 0.1 M NaOH for TYR, ASP, TRP, LEU, ILE and PHE. All other amino acids 10 g/L in 0.1 M HCl. Amino acid mixtures (AAMIX) were made by diluting stock solutions in MilliQ.

2.2 Materials

Syringes were polypropylene from Terumo. Syringe filters were Puradisc 25 AS and spartan 30 from Whatman. Glass scintillation vials were purchased from sigma Aldrich. The sand bath was made internally at the Vrije Universiteit workshop and heated on an IKA rct basic heating and stirring element. The centrifuge used was a Himac CT 15RE. The ultrasonic bath Branson 2510. Pictures of setups can be found in appendix I. XRF spectromembrane Etnom thin film windows and sample cups were purchased from Chemplex industries inc. (Palm City, US).

2.3 Samples

2.3.1 Sample preparation

Post blast battery type firework samples, containing the clay, were provided by the Netherlands forensic institute (the Hague, Netherlands), more on these in the sample information section. Clay plaques were cut out of the firework samples using scissors and a scalpel. After removal the plaques were ground down to powder using a pestle and a Petri dish as a mortar. This powder was then stored in a plastic sample container. To avoid cross-contamination, all tools and surfaces were thoroughly cleaned with deionized water and ethanol before and between samples. For more details see appendix VI.

2.3.2 Sample extraction

For the amino acid and nonspecific sample analysis a simplified sample extraction method loosely based on the soil analysis from Okalebo et al.²⁶ was used. 500 mg ground down clay was placed in a scintillation vial. Then 2 mL of a 100 mM HCl solution was added along with a stirring magnet. The vial was placed in a sand bath which was preheated to 150 °C; boiled for 90 min, removed and left at room temperature to cool down. A 5 mL syringe was then used to transfer the mixture to a 2 mL Eppendorf tube. Followed by centrifugation at 4000 rpm for 10 min to precipitate the particles. The supernatant was then analyzed by CE. For more details see appendix VI. Other sample extraction protocols were tested, these will be discussed in section 3.4.3.

2.4 Instruments and Method

2.4.1 X-ray fluorescence method

XRF experiments were performed using the Vanta handheld XRF from Olympus and the provided Vanta software. For the XRF experiments the sample powder was transferred from the storage container to purpose made sample cups fitted with thin film Etnom windows and pressed down using the back of the plunger from a polypropylene syringe, to create a dense >1 cm layer. Samples were placed on the XRF and analyzed using the GEOCHEM (two beams, 30 seconds each) and SOIL (three beams, 30 seconds each) preprogrammed methods. These methods are capable of measuring 34 and 37 elements respectively. The difference in which elements can be measured is dependent on the energy of the beam, where the analysis time determines the accuracy of the provided abundance. An example table of which elements can be measured is provided in section 3.2. Before every day of measurements the XRF was calibrated using a standard metal alloy. Followed by the samples, which were measured in triplets for both methods.

2.4.2 Capillary electrophoresis method

CE experiments were performed on the PA 800 plus from Beckman Coulter, using 32 Karat software. Separations were done on a 77 cm total length (67 cm length to window), 50 μm ID fused silica capillary. The BGE consisted of 20 mM 2,6-pyridinedicarboxylic acid (PDC), which was added as a complexing agent²⁷ that could help separate small ions; while doubling as an UV-absorbent source to allow indirect UV detection. 0.5 mM CTAH was added to reverse the electroosmotic flow (EOF) allowing fast migrating anions to be separated in the same run as slowly migrating amino acids and carbohydrates²⁸. The pH was adjusted to 12.1 with NaOH (approximately 2% with a 10 M stock solution). Under these conditions most amino acids and carbohydrates will be charged. Before each injection the capillary tips were dipped in water to clean them. Then the capillary was flushed for 3 minutes with the BGE at 9.6 PSI. Samples were introduced by pressure injection for 8 seconds at 1.5 PSI. Voltage was set to -30 kV, unless otherwise specified, the capillary temperature was set to 15 °C, sample storage to 10 °C. Detection with a diode array detection module, wavelength set to 350 nm; the resulting electropherogram was subtracted by a reference channel set at 230 nm. This to make the negative signal from the indirect UV give the appearance of a positive peak in the resulting electropherogram. After every day of measurements, the capillary was flushed with water to improve the longevity of the silica by neutralizing the pH. Before the next use the capillary was reconditioned by flushing with BGE for 20 minutes.

2.5 Data treatment

Data from the XRF software was exported to Microsoft excel and ordered. The ordered data was then analyzed by principal component analysis (PCA) and partial least square regression discriminant analysis (PLS-DA) using the unscrambler X software from Camo analytics. CE data was exported from the 32 Karat software, plotted and analyzed in Microsoft excel.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Sample information

To start our research, we needed a sample set of fireworks. These were provided by the NFI along with information on which city they were produced in, what company imported them and what factory they came from. Our sample set consisted of 35 articles produced in 16 factories from four cities in mountainous south east china: Liuyang, Liling, Yichun and Pingxiang. These cities are close together, see figure 2, but most likely get their clay from specific providers. We know that there are four clay providers in this region; Two in Liuyang, one in Yichun and one in Liling. Although the cities are divided by a mere three-hour drive this is a toll road through a mountainous area. Therefore it can be expected that the factories will use the cheapest and most readily available source, the closest one. This will likely be the case almost everywhere where fireworks are produced. Working with these assumptions the geographical origin of a firework might be ascertained. There are some hurdles to this. Because the cities are so close together all of the clay likely has

Figure 2: Map of the four cities (marked with boxes) where our samples were produced. The dashed line is the border between Hunan and Jiangxi provinces.

similar, if not the same, geological origin and climate. The work done on the clay before the use in fireworks, for example drying or adding a binder, might also influence the purity and original state of the clay. To make data handling and discussion easier all 35 samples were given a code FWS001 – FWS035. Factories were number coded at the NFI, this code was adopted in this paper.

3.2 Study of clay by X-ray fluorescence

XRF was chosen because it is easy to use, non-destructive and has a large capacity for providing information. The sample prep was done using very basic tools and took only a couple of minutes. With automated tools this can be done even faster and with less effort. The clay can easily be recovered from the sample cups with minimal contamination since the Etnom film is specifically made to contain as few interfering compounds as possible. Allowing reanalysis with other methods. The large amount of information is provided by the software in the form of element abundance tables, calculated from spectra which can later be reexamined to validate the computer's results. Two examples of these results for the FWS025 sample are shown in table 1. The SOIL method checks for 37 elements. In our samples not all of these are detected. For most of the fireworks this method gave K, Ti and Fe as the most abundant elements. The GEOCHEM method checks 32 elements; the most abundant being Al, Si, Fe and light elements (LE). Light elements are described as such because, even though X-rays can excite the electrons in all elements to induce photon emission, photons from light elements are too low in energy to reach the detector before getting absorbed by the rest of the sample or the air between the sample and the detector. This lack of signal means light elements are hard to distinguish from the background. For that reason, the GEOCHEM method can only give the total light element (background) value and not that of any specific element lighter than Mg. With simple observations the data can be correlated to the samples; the samples that were more pail and less red showed lower levels Fe and higher levels of Al. But with 35 samples measured in triplet, there is a lot of data, for raw data please contact the author. To handle all this data statistical tools were used. The first step to make analysis more feasible is to reduce the dataset. This was done by removing any element that was not detected in more than 70% of measurements. After this process the GEOCHEM and SOIL method have 21 and 18 elements respectively (elements with * in table 1). These datasets were then combined and transferred to the unscrambler X software, which calculated the PCA and a PLS-DA. The PCA analysis of the combined data is able to group samples together by factory

Table 1: example results from FWS025 measured with both the GEOCHEM and SOIL methods

ELEMENT	GEOCHEM (PPM)	ERROR	SOIL (PPM)	ERROR
MG	ND		NM	
AL*	87516	855	NM	
SI*	189809	654	NM	
P*	725	56	ND	
S*	348	26	139	43
CL	ND		NM	
K*	NM		15578	200
CA	ND		433	37
TI*	6769	105	8100	92
V*	85	12	116	5
CR*	109	18	185	11
MN*	347	15	385	11
FE*	73209	218	72895	267
CO*	ND		284	33
NI*	52	5	ND	
CU*	59	3	49	3
ZN*	137	3	128	3
AS*	37	1	41	2
SE	ND		ND	
RB*	141	2	139	2
SR*	55	1	48	4
Y*	27	1	27	4
ZR*	324	2	370	10
NB*	26	1	23	2
MO	ND		ND	
AG*	74	6	ND	
CD	ND		ND	
SN	ND		ND	
SB	35	11	ND	
BA	NM		215	20
LA	NM		ND	
CE	NM		ND	
PR	NM		ND	
ND	NM		ND	
TA	NM		ND	
W	ND		ND	
HG	6	2	ND	
PB*	31	2	29	2
BI	ND		ND	
TH*	22	3	26	6
U	ND		ND	
LE	652797	1036	NM	

ND = Not detected | NM = Not measured | ppm = parts per million

*elements used for statistics

number reasonably well, as seen in figure 3A. Some are clustered in a particular section like samples from factory 31, where the samples from factories 023, 225 and 255 are both in the top and bottom halves of the graph. However, the samples from these factories are separated based on the specific firework from that factory, figure 3B. This could mean they get clay from two sources, one in Liuyang and one near Liling. Liling and Pingxiang, factories 555 and 239 respectively, are close together which corroborates the expectation that they get clay from the same clay producer located between the cities. The samples from Yichun factory 127 are clearly separated from the others. Because many people have handled the samples and the labels, some factory identifications might be wrong; it is suspected that this is the case for the sample from factory 145 in Yichun, since it is clustered in with the Liuyang samples and because the factory number 145 occurs in both Liuyang and Yichun factory number lists. The wide spread of the other samples, which are all from Liuyang, is likely caused by the use of two separate clay providers in Liuyang

Figure 3: PCA plots based on the combined dataset of 35 samples, with triplets shown as individual points. A: color indicates the city and the label is the factory number. B: color represents the factory and the label is the sample number (FWSO.).

Figure 4: PLS-DA based on combined dataset with element abundance as X variable and province as Y variable. In the circle Liling and Pingxiang datapoints.

along with differences in clay binders. To discriminate between provinces a more adapt method for separating known groups, PLS-DA, was used, figure 4. Provinces are clearly separated, but again the Pingxiang (Jiangxi province) sample is close to the Liling (Hunan province) sample. For the PLS-DA loadings, see appendix II. To simplify the analysis in the future the loadings from the PCA analysis were examined. These loadings signify the amount of influence a variable has on the overall PCA. Figure 5 shows that Al, Si and Fe, the main components of clay, are also the most influential elements for differentiation. Ti and K show some effect, where all other elements show minimal effect compared to Al, Si and Fe. These three elements can all be detected using the GEOCHEM method; making the SOIL method unnecessary for the differentiation of our samples. This also avoids K contamination from the active charge in the firework. Reanalyzing the PCA with only Al, Si and Fe provides a graph very similar to the original.

Figure 5: Loadings the PCA analysis with most influential elements marked.

3.3.1 Method set up

As mentioned previously we know from literature that some clays can contain amino acids^{16,17}. These are promising targets for distinguishing fireworks because they are fairly well researched, stable over time and often occur together allowing the use of ratios as a discriminating factor. Based on these considerations the search for a method which can separate and detect amino acids was started (most amino acids are not UV absorbent). Ultimately a method proposed by Soga and Ross (1999)²⁵ was used. This method has been shown to separate small anions, organic acids, amino acids and carbohydrates in a single run, figure 6A. This variety makes possible the study of amino acids and allows other targets that may also be in clay (carbohydrates, anions) to be considered simultaneously. During CE experiments amino acid mixtures (AAMIX) from standards were used as references for the compounds contained in the clay.

Figure 6: A: Image copied with permission³⁵ from Soga and Ross (1999), for conditions see original publication. B: AAMIX analysed by the adjusted CE method with amino acids assigned through spiked runs. conditions: BGE 20 mM PDC, 0.5 mM CTAH, pH = 12.1. voltage = -21.4 kV, capillary temp = 15 °C, total length 77 cm (67 cm effective), 50 μ m I.D.. Concentration of amino acids 80 mg/L.

Due to limited material availability the method had to be adjusted. The capillary was shortened from 114 cm to 77 cm total length, this decreases the resolution and separating power of the method. Despite this loss in resolution we were still able to separate the amino acids into 12 peaks, figure 6B. ALA and SER were not baseline separated but did show some separation in most runs. The group of VAL, PRO and MET showed no separation at all. HIS, PHE and (iso)LEU again showed some but not baseline separation. Where TYR and TRP are displayed as negative peaks because they absorb UV at 230 nm, the same as our reference channel. A thing of note, the UV absorbent additive PDC acts as a complexing agent as well, this means that the separation of the amino acids is not linear with m/z values. This goes some way to explaining why MET has a similar migration time to the lighter VAL and PRO, 149 m/z, 117 m/z and 115 m/z respectively.

Some method development was required to obtain consistent separation of these 12 peaks. The first overnight experiments showed changes, figure 7A, in separation over time. The first run of the day showed 11 peaks; the same standard was tested several times with new buffer vials each time, after twelve runs 4 additional peaks appear and some peaks, such as the peak around 19 minutes, have shifted by as much as 3 minutes. This 12th

Figure 7: A: The a: 1st and b: 12th measurement without oil overlay. B: The a: 4th and b: 18th run with oil overlay. conditions: BGE 20 mM PDC, 0.5 mM CTAH, pH = 12.1. voltage = -21.4 kV, capillary temp = 15 °C, total length 77 cm (67 cm effective), 50 μm I.D.. Concentration of amino acids 80 mg/L

separation had higher resolution than the first run. However, it was not repeatable and not enough time was available to optimize the method to obtain similar results. This lack of robustness in the method made peak matching difficult and unreliable. After exploring possible causes such as capillary conditioning, capillary temperature and repeated use of BGE vials, it was discovered that these effects were caused by evaporation of the BGE. To prevent this evaporation, a 150 μL layer of mineral oil was added to the BGE vials²⁹. This oil layer sits on top of the BGE and prevents contact with air, strongly reducing the evaporation that occurs. The effects of the oil layer can be seen in figure 7B. Even after more than 16 runs the separation stayed consistent and no peak switching occurred. Now that the method was consistent and repeatable the clay samples could be analyzed.

3.3.2 Clay analysis by capillary electrophoresis

3.3.2.1 Amino acids

An experiment was set up to find the amino acids in the clay samples. Three runs were performed: the amino mix standard, a clay sample (FWS001) and the same clay sample spiked with the amino mix standard. Where the clay sample was extracted using the method described in 2.3.2. In figure 8 the peak at 5.1 min is a peak caused by HCl. The peak at 7.6 min, the ALA/SER peak in the AAMIX, is the only peak aside from the HCl and BGE peaks that occurs in all three electropherograms. ALA and SER are the only amino

Figure 8: Comparison top to bottom a: FWS025, b: 50:50 FWS025:AAMIX and c: AAMIX. BGE 20 mM PDC, 0.5 mM CTAH, pH = 12.1. voltage = -30 kV, capillary temp = 15 °C, total length 77 cm (67 cm effective), 50 μm I.D. Concentration of amino acids in AAMIX 80 mg/L, clay concentration 250 mg/mL.

acids which can be shown to be in this firework clay sample. In the Soga and Ross paper the ALA and SER peaks were resolved, with our limited means we were unable to achieve this level of resolution. In the firework clay sample this ALA/SER peak is broad, so improved resolution is required to distinguish between the two and exclude unrelated compounds. However, the clay samples did also show several non-amino acid peaks, therefore this method was found to be viable for nonspecific sample discrimination.

3.3.2.2 Nonspecific sample discrimination

After discovering amino acids are not an advantageous target for our group of samples, a switch was made to a nonspecific discrimination. Using the standard extraction and CE methods, 28 out of 35 firework clay plaques were analyzed. In appendix III all electropherograms are provided. The differences between samples are subtle but big enough for visual sample discrimination. To illustrate this the peaks that appear clearly in (almost) all electropherograms are numbered in figure 9. Peaks 1, 3 and 7 were consistently present in controls along with a small broad peak which overlaps with peak 9. Peak 2 was baseline separated from peak 3 in some samples and fully incorporated in others. Where peaks 8 and 10 appear as shoulders but are never fully separated from peak 9. Figure 9 displays three distinct electropherograms from fireworks made in three

Figure 9: comparison of top to bottom a: FWS011, b: FWS024 and c: FWS035. BGE 20 mM PDC, 0.5 mM CTAH, pH = 12.1. voltage = -30 kV, capillary temp = 15 °C, total length 77 cm (67 cm effective), 50 μ m I.D. Concentration clay sample 250 mg/mL.

different cities; FWS011 from Liuyang, FWS024 from Liling and FWS035 from Yichun. Since the clay used is that from close by, these three factories use separate clay providers but similar clay types. An attempt was made to analyze the data using automated peak identification and comparing ratios. This was however not feasible because, first the baseline was not stable over the whole chromatogram, second some peaks that were clearly different in visual inspections were shifted enough to be indistinguishable when looking at raw data and third because some peaks were negative in intensity due to absorption at 230 nm, which analysis programs are notoriously bad at identifying. To do proper analysis a more stable system is required. However, these samples were extracted using the same proportions and extraction method, the same HCl solution was used, the same BGE batch, measured on the same day with the same CE method and used oil overlays to improve robustness. Here improvement is unlikely. With more time and manual adjustments, the data could be made to be more comparable, from a data analysis standpoint. By visual inspection alone the electropherograms are easily distinguishable, it is however difficult to group samples together because the identities of peaks are unknown. Since all the peaks are unknown it is unsound to appoint a characteristic peak to base our grouping on. The information of which factory the sample is from should give us a starting point for grouping but electropherograms from the same batch of fireworks are sometimes more dissimilar than samples from separate cities. All of this makes data analysis too difficult for the scope of this project. However, there is a positive conclusion from this work: the visual inspection did confirm our expectation of differences between the clay plaques. Informing that with a different method or other techniques, such as CE-MS, these differences can be explored and utilized.

3.4.3 Sample extraction

To obtain the maximum amount of information from the clay the effectiveness of sample extraction was investigated. Because the method uses indirect UV detection, the limit of detection is low, the amount of sample required for proper signal needed to be found. The standard extraction (section 2.3.2) was performed using 100, 200, 400, 500 and 1000 mg of clay. The 100 and 200 mg runs showed fewer peaks than the others. The 500 mg showed increased signal compared to the 400 mg and so did the 1000 mg, however the increase in signal from 500 to a 1000 mg was not big enough to justify the added cost to sample amount. 500 mg was used for further experiments. Next the amount of acid required was tested. Extractions with 0, 15, 100, 200, 1000 mM HCl were compared. 0 and 15 mM produced fewer peaks than the other three concentrations. The 200 and 1000 mM showed increased peak intensities compared to 100 mM, but also distorted the baseline more and pushed all the peaks to later times. 100 mM was used for further experiments.

Because amino acid experiments show only a single unresolved ALA/SER peak, they were ruled out as a candidate for distinction. What is left is a CE method which separates negatively charged ions. The original extraction method with acid makes sense for the extraction of amphoteric compounds like amino acids from clay, since it protonates the metal oxide groups causing reduced ionic interaction with the positively charged amino acids. One would expect an adverse effect on the retention of anions, since protonation reduces the repulsion between negatively charged groups and promotes hydrogen bridging. To test this and explore other acids, the same general extraction was tested using pure H₂O, 100 mM H₂SO₄, 100 mM NaOH and compared to the original 100 mM HCl as extraction solvents. The results are shown in figure 10. The new extraction methods did not show extra peaks compared to the HCl extraction nor extra peaks between samples. However, the NaOH extraction was far more stable in baseline, had no negative signal and system peaks obscured fewer sample peaks. Because of this, the peak ratios are now a far more attainable source for discrimination. In future

Figure 10: Comparison HCl and NaOH with two samples FWS025 and FWS035. BGE 20 mM PDC, 0.5 mM CTAH, pH = 12.1. voltage = -30 kV, capillary temp = 15 °C, total length 77 cm (67 cm effective), 50 μ m I.D.

work this could be investigated as an effective method for sample analysis. Sulfuric acid did not show improvement over HCl, electropherograms are in appendix IV.

Another sample extraction component that was investigated is the mechanical part of the extraction. A random firework plaque was chosen (FWS025) and extracted using 10 and 60 min of stirring, 10 and 60 min of ultra-sonification and 30 and 90 min stirring at 150 °C. Both under acidic and alkaline conditions. From the resulting electropherograms, appendix V, we can see that under basic conditions the only peaks that change with the type or time of extraction are the peaks that are also in control samples. No additional information is gained from the use of mechanics. Under acidic conditions there are differences that are not directly related to the control peaks, along with higher peak intensities. But these are big messes of peaks, so to say that the full extraction of 90 min heating is worth the effort would be controversial. These results do show that the extraction method used for the main part of this article was valid, just possibly not the best available. This also means that for any further research easier and less time-consuming sample extraction can be used.

4. Conclusion and future perspectives

In this work a method has been set up for the preparation and extraction of compounds from firework clay plaques for the analysis by XRF and indirect UV detection CE. The statistical results of the XRF data can group the studied samples by province, city and even by factory. Where the CE study showed alanine and/or serine are the only amino acids which could possibly be detected by the chosen method to be in our clay samples. Nonspecific CE analysis using the standard extraction method showed differences between firework samples, corroborating the differences shown by the XRF. Furthermore, even though the NaOH extraction shows no additional information compared to the HCl extraction, it was more stable and is therefore a better candidate for nonspecific discrimination. All in all, when combined, the tools set up in this work look promising for creating a chemical fingerprint which can individualize fireworks and distinguish their origin.

More work is still to be done to validate the methods. The XRF data analysis can group samples, however it did so with a small data set. A larger dataset will be set up to refine the PCA and PLS-DA analysis, along with an established protocol and validation with the more accurate static XRF³⁰. The CE method using NaOH extraction will be tested on its repeatability and robustness, to find out if this analysis really is suitable for nonspecific sample distinction. Since the PDC used as a BGE component is also fluorescent the possibility of indirect fluorescence detection will be investigated for an increase in

detection sensitivity^{31,32}. The clay samples will also be analyzed by CE-MS in order to identify peaks and to make the nonspecific specific, creating a more trusted and reliable fingerprint. This technique is also needed to identify binders used or added compounds.

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7. Appendix

- I. Sample extraction setups. On the left the sand bath setup with caps loosened and stirring magnets inside. On the right ultrasonification bath setup; vials filled with 10 mL solution, taped with clear office tape to a Styrofoam falcon tube holder. This to keep the vials upright and floating in the bath, section 2.2

- II. Loadings PLS-DA comparing provinces based on combined GEOCHEM and SOIL XRF datasets, section 3.2.

III. Electropherograms of all 28 CE measured clay samples, Section 3.3.2.2. For conditions and method see sections 2.3 and 2.4.2.

IV. Extraction with H_2SO_4 versus HCl , section 3.4.3. For conditions and method see sections 2.3 and 2.4.2.

V. A: comparison mechanical test with NaOH. B: comparison mechanical test HCl, section 3.4.3.

VI. Advise:

This part is written for anyone who will continue with this project. It is an account of problems I ran into and tips to make things a little easier. What we did for sample prep to be more specific than the main paper:

- Paper was laid down to catch dust and particles from the work for easier cleanup
- the clay was cut out of the cardboard using scissors and a scalpel. Some force was needed for both because the cardboard is layered extensively and thus is quite tough to get through.
- The sides of the clay were scraped with the scalpel to remove some of the surface contaminants.
- The clay was placed in a Petri dish (the only cleanable surface we had available to grind down the clay).
- The clay was ground down to a fine powder using a pestle where the Petri dish was used as a "mortar". (fine powder is vague but also hard to describe, the
- Then transferred to plastic sample cups (from the NFI)
- Mark clearly which sample is which.
- To avoid sample cross contamination all the instruments and dishes used were cleaned several times with ethanol, water, ethanol.
- Throw away paper and lightly clean the surface.
- Repeat

These were then used for both the XRF and the CE measurements.

For the XRF:

- Again, lay down paper for easier clean up
- Lay the film over the ring
- Place the rest of the cup to where it will fit in the ring
- Then press down with evenly distributed force on the top
- Don't get discouraged it will likely tear often during this process.
- (I tore off the access film from the sides to avoid clay getting stuck on it and thus cross contamination if they are stored in the same place, but be careful doing this, it could tear the whole film).
- Then fill the cup with the clay, approximately 1 cm layer. This does not have to be exact, but try to make sure it is at least 1 cm.

- (I removed the plunger from a 10mL syringe and used this to move the clay, I choose this because it was used later anyway, try to avoid using stuff that adds contaminants unless needed)
- Press down the clay using the back of the plunger from a 10 mL syringe. Be careful not to tear the film. If it is on a properly flat surface, you can put quite a bit of pressure on it because without the pressure difference between points it will not tear.
- Place the lid on top and mark clearly which sample it is
- Then wipe down the cup with a KIMTECH or similar not abrasive wipe. Again, to avoid contaminations.
- Place it as central as possible on the XRF.

For the CE extraction from the main part of the paper

- Turn on the heating element from the sand bath so it can heat up while you are preparing samples.
- Weigh 500mg clay from the sample cup.
- Place in scintillation vial.
- Take a small stir flow (stirring magnet), wash it ethanol, water, ethanol and place in the vial.
- Add 2 mL of a 100 mM HCl solution.
- Place in the sand bath, cover with cap but loosen it slightly so air can escape and there is no dangerous gas build up. (try not to use more than six vials at once because the stirring is magnets won't work properly if they are too far from the center)
- Turn on stirring.
- Use a wooden spatula to move some sand to the vial, such that the sand reaches the same level outside the vial as the liquid inside the vial. This to increase coverage and gain more consistent heating of the sample.
- Let stir and heat for 90 min. (the movement from the stirring magnets may tip them over so check regularly to see if they are still upright)
- Remove from the sand bath. For me a pair of gloves was heat resisted enough to pick them up but be careful not to burn yourself and maybe use a thicker layer of insulation.
- Let it cool down. It is a small volume so this should be quick.

- Use a 5 mL syringe to take up as much sample as you can. Some clay will stick to the sides or at the bottom, but after all the stirring the fluid should be homogeneous enough.
- Put in to 2 mL Eppendorf. Be careful with bubble formation when pushing the syringe, they can pop and spray. Make sure everything is closed to avoid contamination and wear proper protection.
- Centrifuge at 4000g for 10 min. remember to counterbalance properly. Try to avoid shaking too much afterwards, this could dislodge particles.

This was the method used. Based on experiments performed at the end of my internship, I recommend simplifying this and changing the solvent. I recommend:

- 500 mg clay
- dissolving it in a 100 mM NaOH solution
- Add flow magnet
- Stir for 10 min
- Transfer to 2 mL Eppendorf with 5 mL syringe
- Centrifuge for 20 min (NaOH mixtures needed some more time)

Alternatively, what I have not been able to test but might reduce the sample prep time extensively is; to add the clay and the NaOH 100 mM solution in an Eppendorf directly and ultra-sonifying that for 10 min. We did not use this because we needed higher temperatures and larger volumes from the start.

For 50 mL CE background electrolyte:

- Weigh 167.2 mg PDC
- Place in bottle and use 50 mL MilliQ water to wash the remainders into the bottle.
- Pipette in 35.5 μ L CTAH
- Add a stirring flow. (again, clean with ethanol, water, ethanol)
- Calibrate the pH meter.
- Turn on stirring
- Adjust the pH to 12.1 with NaOH. I used a 10M solution to get close and then dripped in a 1M solution to reach 12.1. (The amount needed can change significantly between batches, you can start with 200 μ L of 10M and then add as you go).

This recipe should give you approximately 50 mL BGE with:

- 20 mM PDC
- 0.5 mM CTAH
- pH = 12.1

For the oil layer in CE

- In the appropriate CE vial, add 1.25 mL of the BGE (I pipetted against the left side of the vial because I am right-handed)
- Make sure there are no bubbles in your BGE, by tapping or using a pipette tip (these will get trapped under the oil layer)
- Slowly take up 150 µL mineral oil, turn the vial 180° and pipette against the left wall again so it does not touch the BGE and flows down better. (I had some trouble reusing oil pipette tips, they formed bubbles when being emptied completely, which then get sucked up again when sucking up the next one. (So, I usually just used a new one for every vial).
- Make sure to remove any bubbles left at the top.

CE settings

Initial Conditions PDA Detector Initial Conditions Time Program								
	Time (min)	Event	Value	Duration	Inlet vial	Outlet vial	Summary	
1		Rinse - Pressure	1.0 psi	0.10 min	BI:A6	BO:A6	forward	tip clean water
2		Rinse - Pressure	9.6 psi	3.00 min	BI:A1	BO:A1	forward, In vial inc 10	Rinse BGE
3		Inject - Pressure	1.5 psi	6.0 sec	SI:C1	BO:A1	Override, forward	Injection 10% length to window
4	0.00	Separate - Voltage	30.0 KV	20.00 min	BI:B1	BO:B1	0.17 Min ramp, reverse polarity, In / Out vial inc 5	
5	20.00	End						
6								

Initial Conditions | PDA Detector Initial Conditions | Time Program

Electropherogram scan data

Acquisition enabled

Data rate: 4 Hz

Scan range from 190 to 350 nm

Electropherogram channel data

Data Rate: 4 Hz

	Acquisition enabled	Reference channel	Wavelength (nm)	Bandwidth (nm)
Channel 1:	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	350	10
Channel 2:	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	214	10
Channel 3:	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	230	10
Peak detect:	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	250	120

Filter

High sensitivity
 Normal
 High resolution

Peak width (points): 16-25

Relay 1: Off
 On

Relay 2: Off
 On

Reference channel

Wavelength: 230 nm
Bandwidth: 10 nm

Absorbance signal

Direct
 Indirect

Initial Conditions | PDA Detector Initial Conditions | Time Program

Auxiliary data channels

Voltage max: 30.0 kV
 Current max: 100.0 μ A
 Power
 Pressure

Mobility channels

Mobility
 Apparent Mobility
 Plot trace after voltage ramp

Analog output scaling

Factor: 1

Temperature

Cartridge: 15.0 $^{\circ}$ C
Sample storage: 10.0 $^{\circ}$ C

Peak detect parameters

Threshold: 2
Peak width: 9

Trigger settings

Wait for external trigger
 Wait until cartridge coolant temperature is reached
 Wait until sample storage temperature is reached

Inlet trays

Buffer: 36 vials
Sample: 48 vials

Outlet trays

Buffer: 36 vials
Sample: 48 vials

VII. Things to try

Due to the limited scope of this paper, several options for analysis of clay were not explored. During my internship the most common phrase I heard was XRD^{20,21,22}, a technique commonly utilized in the field of mineral analysis. At the start of our project this was considered as one of the techniques to use, since it can provide the crystal

structure which in turn can identify types of clay. However, when we found out that our samples were all from a small region in china, a three-hour drive apart, we reconsidered. The climate and geology of the clay sources are similar and therefor the minerals that comprise the clay too common. We still believe that this is the case, if it were not for chemometric tools. The chemometrics used for the XRF experiments showed good separation power based on just three elements. This makes XRD a more promising technique for the future and we can stop getting that suggestion. Another common suggestion was using a non-portable XRF as opposed to the portable variety; they are more accurate than the handheld and can measure lighter elements such as carbon and nitrogen (down to beryllium depending on the instrument)³⁰. The portable XRF is not sensitive enough to fully quantify an element, where the stationary XRF utilizes better optics and geometry to obtain the sensitivity needed for total quantification. This extended sensitivity and lighter element information could be useful to validate the data from the portable XRF, while also providing further information on the clay. However, the portable variety should be sufficiently effective for our purposes on its own. Another suggestion still, was the use of isotope ratios. A group at the geology department of the Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam has been working on geographical mapping of the Netherlands based on strontium 67 and 66 isotope ratios³⁴. If such maps become available for the regions where fireworks are produced this could be a viable target for our work. A similar method is already in use for the geological origin of cocaine, which uses $\delta^{2}\text{H}$, $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ isotopes to find the location where the coca plants were grown³⁵. These ratios can be explored using either IRMS (magnetic sector MS)³⁴ or with ICP-MS³⁶. As a next step in this research there should be an exploration to gain more information on these clays and then decide on a target for discrimination.

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